

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation. Nowadays, as the world develops, it is very important to learn world languages. Especially, learning English is becoming a global demand. The reason is that the database of many useful things on a global scale is in English.

Key words. English language, native language, global demand, Futurologists, self-education.

Currently, the English language occupies a significant place in the life of any person. Just a few years ago it was perceived by everyone as foreign. But over time, its role has increased so much that it is now considered international. In other words, it is the global language of the entire world community. Futurologists say that in less than a hundred years there will be no language barrier, and people everywhere will begin to communicate in English. English is the native language of more than 400 million people living in 12 countries of the world, which include: USA, England, Canada, New Zealand, Australia, etc. In more than 30 countries of the world, such as India, Singapore, Philippines, Malaysia, and many others, it is widely used on a national scale along with national languages. Nowadays, any educated person is simply obliged to speak English, since it is his key to further self-education and self-improvement. The English language allows you not only to improve your intellectual abilities, but also to touch the work of great people: you can read the most outstanding works in their originals, listen to musical compositions that are known throughout the world, and understand their essence. When traveling around the world, you cannot do without knowing the language. In order to avoid getting into an awkward situation and simply feel confident in a foreign country, you need to know English. Then, those who speak the language will not have to explain themselves on their fingers. You can freely communicate with people of different nationalities, learn a lot about the culture and traditions of foreign countries.

Knowledge of the English language makes it possible to study at prestigious foreign universities, since proficiency in it is one of the most important selection criteria for admission. In order to get a prestigious job in a large organization, you need to be fluent in the language.

Knowledge of English allows you to communicate with business partners, take part in international conferences, read international magazines and newspapers. English plays an increasingly important role in such areas of human activity as science, technology, economics, trade, sports, and tourism. This language has become the international language of aviation and shipping. Almost 80% of all data stored in modern computers is presented in English. Instructions for equipment, computer applications, the press, and television are often limited to this language only. English serves as the working language of the vast majority of international scientific, technical, political and professional conferences, symposia and

seminars. This foreign language is increasingly penetrating everyday life. This language ranks first in the world among foreign languages studied in secondary and higher schools, as well as in various courses in the adult education system. Of course, in order to learn any language, you need the desire and desire for knowledge, you need to be patient and diligently, step by step, overcome all the difficulties in this process that will certainly arise. In the process of learning English, a person faces a problem related to the fact that the English language has many faces. Its diversity is believed to be due to the fact that all words are written and pronounced completely differently. And there are very few words that are both written and pronounced. But this is not the only problem facing all students of this language. The difficulty lies in the fact that in English there are a very large number of tenses, which does not correspond at all to the Russian language, and it is quite difficult to remember these tenses in relation to their characteristics. It can also be noted that the problems of learning English are related to the fact that this language has a very wide variety of sounds that are formed by different combinations of letters. One has only to say that there are 26 letters in English, but about 44 sounds. But that's not all. When it comes to learning English, it is necessary to mention knowledge of a number of rules, and, perhaps most importantly, a sufficient amount of words necessary for communication. English is 3,000 words for conversational level, 7,000 words for business level and over 10,000 words for academic level. Based on these data, you can understand the amount of information that will have to not only be remembered well, but also understood and assimilated. On the other hand, learning English, although difficult, is very interesting. Indeed, nowadays there are a large number of modern technologies with which you can overcome all the difficulties of learning English. Recently, it has become especially popular to learn English using the Internet. The use of information technologies leads to overcoming age, time, and space barriers and provides the opportunity to learn throughout life. The Internet helps to develop speaking skills and abilities, as well as in teaching vocabulary and grammar, provides the opportunity for authentic communication with real interlocutors on current topics, creates conditions for obtaining the necessary information located anywhere in the world: regional studies material, news from the lives of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc. It should be noted that, despite the lack of free time, young people are able to spend almost the entire night at the computer, experiencing positive emotions. As an information system, the Internet offers its users a variety of information and resources. Services provided by the Internet may include: email and chats (for developing writing skills), teleconferencing, video conferencing (for developing speaking skills), the ability to publish your own page and post it on the website, access to information resources (sources of additional materials) , reference directories, search engines, online conversation. For this purpose, programs such as ICQ, Skype, Yahoo, etc. are used. Interactive communication helps to study English in more depth. After all, theory alone is not enough without practice. And the best practice is to have a conversation via the Internet with native speakers: English, American. The on-line system is being improved every year. Using the latest programs, you can record your results and analyze them. The possibility of self-control allows you to individualize the process of teaching foreign languages and increase the degree of interest in the results. Thus, when learning English using the Internet, you can solve a number of problems: - develop reading skills and abilities, directly using online materials of varying degrees of complexity; - improve listening skills based on authentic audio texts; - practice

grammar and improve writing skills; - replenish your vocabulary with vocabulary of a modern foreign language; - train pronunciation; - get acquainted with the culture and traditions of the country of the language being studied. Thus, learning English is a process of acquiring knowledge that is vital in a modern society developing in the direction of globalization. Therefore, English is an important component in the life of a modern person, and everyone can find more than one reason for learning it and improving their skills.

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